

Contributions of Social Technology to Local Development in Ecuador

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Abstract

Background: Rural communities often face significant challenges regarding economic and social development. This study examines the transformative role of social technology in the parish of Salinas de Guaranda in Ecuador.

Objective: To analyse the contributions of social technology to local development in Salinas de Guaranda in Ecuador.

Methodology: A case study was used to analyse the contributions of social technology to community development in Salinas de Guaranda, Ecuador. Data collection was carried out through interviews, observation, and literature review. Ten semi-structured interviews were conducted with key community stakeholders, chosen for their knowledge of the history of the community process and its contribution to local development. Each interview lasted approximately 45 minutes. Observation of daily activities and literature review complemented the interviews, providing historical and contextual data.

Results: Social technology in Salinas de Guaranda was adapted in three stages: first, to improve the organisational infrastructure; then, to strengthen processes; and finally, to optimise productive systems. Active community participation in decision-making and the inclusion of external knowledge were crucial for local development in Salinas de Guaranda.

Unique Contribution: The study, through a case study in Salinas de Guaranda, Ecuador, has revealed the role of social technology in local development, showing how social technology can transform rural communities.

Conclusion: Social technology in Salinas de Guaranda, Ecuador, has had a positive impact on the community and has been key to its local development, by improving infrastructure, productive processes and community participation.

Key Recommendation: Research should be extended to other rural communities to compare experiences and further analyse the long-term impact of social technology. The role of public policies and academia in promoting social technologies for local development should also be explored.

Keywords: technology; social technology; organization; local development

Introduction

In its annual report on the Social Panorama of Latin America, the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean [CEPAL] (2021) indicates that 187 million people live in poverty and 70 million in extreme poverty. Between 2015 and 2019, poverty and extreme poverty increased by 0.7 and 0.9 percentage points, respectively. In Ecuador, poverty grew by 1.5% and extreme poverty by 1.1% (CEPAL, 2021). In Ecuador, the lack of attention by the governments in power has generated permanent processes of impoverishment; therefore, for Santos (2003) cited in Naranjo (2012), alternatives to the large-scale industrialisation model must be sought as a source of development. Thus, local development is seen as "a tool to improve the living conditions of the population, through concerted action between different socioeconomic, public and private agents, aimed at taking advantage of existing endogenous resources more efficiently and sustainably" (Mballa, 2017, p. 108).

In any development process, technologies are essential for society to adapt to the different circumstances that arise; therefore, it is important to consider new technological alternatives that offer solutions to real problems and seek social progress without limiting themselves to a specific sector or field of action (Calanchez et al., 2022).

Despite the poverty rates indicated previously in Ecuador, there are success stories such as those experienced in the parish of Salinas de Guaranda in Ecuador, which with the creation of the "Gruppo Salinas" has managed to reduce poverty and exclusion rates (Samaniego, 2021), managing to boost the economy in Salinas, establishing community businesses, savings and credit cooperatives, stores selling dairy products, confectionery, chocolates, textiles, etc., typical of the town, whose success is primarily due to the social technologies implemented in the aforementioned population.

This descriptive-explanatory research uses the qualitative method based on a case study to analyse social technology's contributions to local development in Salinas de Guaranda, Ecuador. The analysis revealed three stages in the community process: improvement of organisational infrastructure, strengthening processes, and optimising productive systems. It is essential to analyse how social technology helps overcome poverty and exclusion in rural communities. The contributions of social technology in Salinas de Guaranda offer valuable lessons for other communities seeking their development.

Objective of the study

The study analyses the contributions of social technology to local development in Salinas de Guaranda, Ecuador. It identifies the characteristics, properties and understanding of the use of social technologies in the community process, allowing Salinas de Guaranda to move from a tax-paying economy to an export-oriented one.

Review of Related Literature

Social Technology

Today, technology has become artificially autonomous from values, closed in on itself, and in technological societies whose direction does not consider ends other than technology, with profits and losses (Gómez, 2021). Technological dependence has also affected Latin America. Automation in rural areas caused unemployment and peasant migration to cities. In Ecuador, evangelists' introduction of pocket radios caused changes in habits, values and loss of interest in community problems, generating a society dominated by technology (Gómez, 2021).

Therefore, it is crucial to establish dialogues that build bridges between scientific and non-scientific knowledge in producing knowledge, from which real solutions to specific problems are provided. These signs encourage us to consider new points of view related to the development of social technologies. These are "a way of developing and implementing technologies (of product, process and organisation), oriented to the generation of dynamics of social and economic inclusion and sustainable development" (Binimelis-Espinoza, 2017, p. 453).

Social technology is born from Latin American critical thinking on the development models adopted in Latin America (Torres & Naranjo, 2022). Being inclusive and participatory, they promote democratic practices and collaboration in generating ideas. Social technologies seek to:

- Participation of the local community throughout the process, from definition to solution of the problem.
- Local knowledge is combined with expert or technical knowledge (often foreign), which is not neglected but integrated and assimilated.
- It seeks to benefit from local skills and experiences and local resources, such as endogenous resources.
- Look for possibilities for re-application. Re-applicability allows a social technology to be adapted to a new context, adjusting it to local needs and adding new values.
- The processes of developing and re-applying social technology seek to reduce the disruption of natural, social, and cultural environments.

Social technologies are conceptualized as intrinsically political processes, whose actions must arise from discussion processes based on inclusion, pluralism, participatory equality, autonomy and the common good (Cardoso et al., 2019). Therefore, it is essential to select categories that allow identifying the characteristics of a social technology, which are described in the following table:

Table 1. Categories of Social Technology

Categories	Definition	Features
Inclusion	Inclusion of new individual and collective actors in public policy decision-making	Collective decisions, without pressure, dialogue, clarity, and understanding.
Pluralism	Various actors (market, State, and civil society) have different perspectives on decision-making regarding public policies.	Make decisions collectively, without pressure, and be transparent and understandable.
Participatory equality	Equality of effective action in public policy decision-making processes.	Collective decision making without coercion and understanding.
Autonomy:	Several actors in public policies share decision-making power.	Make decisions collectively, without pressure, and be transparent and understandable.
Discussion process	Discussion of problems through negotiated authority in the public sphere. Facilitates public discussion of problems, promoting equal rights and understanding between social actors.	Transparency, understanding, dialogue and understanding.
Common good	Social welfare is achieved through republican practice	Transparency, understanding and intelligibility.

Source: Taken from (Cardoso et al., 2019, pp. 195 - 198)

Social technologies express democratic participation in the construction of the future, where society regulates technology for the collective well-being, not the market. If possible, the foundations of technological determinism can be incorporated.

Local Development

In 1949, Harry Truman, president-elect of the United States, popularised development by proposing fair and democratic trade for the progress of underdeveloped areas, based on scientific and technological advances (Treacy, 2022). This thinking has been widely practised in our region; in the 1960s and 1970s, development plans in Latin America focused on two types of productive clusters: development poles and industrial complexes. These models are based on the idea that “propulsive or driving industries are dominant economic actors in the economic growth of regions and localities” (Tenório & Monje-Reyes, 2010, p. 52); however, poverty rates in their respective regions have not been eliminated or reduced (Sosa et al., 2020). Thus, local development emerges as an alternative to combat poverty, understood not only as material deficiencies, but also as the lack of equal access to social resources and opportunities, and is established as a tool to improve living conditions through the concerted action of different socioeconomic agents, efficiently and

sustainably taking advantage of endogenous resources (Mballa, 2017, p. 108). It is characterized by:

- Localities, NGOs and public institutions play a relevant role in economic development.
- The analysis of local or regional economic development incorporates multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary aspects.
- The analysis of externalities, including technological ones, plays a relevant role.
- Success in today's competitive environment relies on creating and accumulating local social capital, which drives productivity and cooperation.

Local development admits reciprocity, cooperation, and solidarity to benefit the socioeconomic, political, cultural, and environmental well-being of the local area (Tenório & Monje-Reyes, 2010).

Methodology

In the present longitudinal non-experimental research, a descriptive-explanatory study was defined, with a qualitative methodology with a phenomenological approach, whose "concern is not primarily to measure, but to qualify and describe the social phenomenon from determining features, as they are perceived by the same elements that are within the situation studied" (Bernal, 2010, p. 60), allowing to interpret, search and understand individuals and their processes, taking into account their past and current circumstances (Álvarez- Gayou, 2003). The objective was to identify the characteristics, properties and understanding of the use of social technologies in the community process of Salinas de Guaranda, Ecuador. To do this, the qualitative case study method was widely used in social sciences, administration, education, politics and technological development (Martínez, 2006). The data collection was carried out through observation, bibliographic review and interviews, applying the concept of data triangulation for greater depth and precision in the research (Álvarez-Gayou, 2003). Ten semi-structured interviews were conducted with key actors from foundations, cooperatives and companies in the parish of Salinas, each lasting approximately 45 minutes. The inclusion criteria were their leadership role and their knowledge of the history of the community process and its contribution to local development. The bibliographic review allowed contextualising the history of Salinas, while observation facilitated the understanding of daily activities. The researcher acted as a complete observer, where the researcher remains hidden while observing, without the observed being aware of it.

Ethical considerations

Prior to the interviews, participants were informed by telephone about the research objective, and their consent for recording was requested, ensuring confidentiality and exclusive use for academic purposes. At the beginning of each interview, the request for consent for the recording of the interview was reiterated, and the participants accepted it.

Results and Discussion

Salinas is located in the northeastern area of Guaranda in the province of Bolívar (Ecuador), at an altitude of 3,550 meters above sea level. It has been a civil parish since 1884, whose main activity was to obtain salt from the saltwater springs from which the town takes its name, surviving in three ways: work on the farm, crops and barter (they exchanged salt for basic products for subsistence), a condition that prevented the inhabitants from being within the market system (Naranjo, 2012). These conditions of exploitation and poverty were the triggers that started the community process

that began in 1970 with the arrival of a Salesian mission, thus allowing a social transformation. This process went through three stages (Naranjo et al., 2018):

- Construction of basic infrastructure.
- Develop production and marketing systems.
- Decentralisation of the productive system.

First stage: Construction of basic infrastructure

At this stage, the community house and the school were built; as well as, the improvement of the road infrastructure and the school; and, the provision of electricity and water; the first productive initiatives were undertaken such as: the production of crafts with sheep's wool and the construction of the first cheese factory. Not all initiatives were successful; however, each difficulty was overcome thanks to the minga (Naranjo et al., 2018). The minga consists of the solidarity and collective work of the members of a social group to carry out social welfare work (Naranjo, 2012).

Salinas managed, with difficulty... let's say, to get out of a situation of poverty, a situation that improved your quality of life... with people who practically did not finish studying, he has achieved what Salinas has achieved being recognized for his community companies... they have had the opportunity to study and are professionals (Interviewee 1)
Of course... there is always consultation, conversation, and discussion in council, and that is where the best solutions and criteria come from (Interviewee 4)

In these interviews, it is important to mention that the organisation contributed to incorporating previously excluded individual and collective actors; this citizen participation positively impacts the community, directly contributing to local development (Tenório & Monje-Reyes, 2010).

The Salinas Savings and Credit Cooperative (COACCSAL) was the first organisation founded in Salinas. It promoted savings and credit among its members and their involvement in cheese and sheep wool production projects. Later, FUNORSAL, PRODUCOP, TEXSAL, etc. emerged (Naranjo et al., 2018). The Association for the Social Development of Artisans of Salinas (TEXAL) plays a fundamental role in integrating women in productive processes.

This association was formed to make fabrics from sheep and llama wool. TEXAL, despite not achieving significant financial development over these fifty years, constitutes the backbone for incorporating women's participation in productive activities in the area and is a way of entering other organisations in the community process (Naranjo et al., 2018, p. 144).

The Salinas Peasant Organisations Foundation (FUNORSAL) has played an important role in Salinas. Through management and accompaniments, it has promoted productive processes and provided road access.

If almost the entire community, directly or indirectly, receives training, people who come from other communities also receive training, education, support... Having a road crew to

open roads. This foundation opened local roads within the parish, approximately 180 km² of roads to reach all our communities (Interviewee 2).

This interview highlights that the type of Social Technology used in this first stage is the organisation, “understood as a structure that brings together diverse people to be able to promote activities of common interest” (Naranjo et al., 2018). This allows the community, through community work, mangas, participation, and integration of the population, to satisfy their basic needs and integrate into productive processes such as cheese and textile production.

Second stage: Development of production and marketing systems

Not all the projects undertaken in Salinas achieved their objectives. The first experience with dairy products was a failure, so the first cheese factory had to close.

We knew (I speak in plural out of habit) how to make “Cordoban” cheeses, but we lacked access to the market, which the bosses had, and the administrative management left much to be desired. Even today, experience confirms that 90% of the problem in this task is not the cheese, but the organisation. Establishing an efficient administrative system and securing the market is the task of the human group as a whole and cannot be left to chance (Polo, 2021, p. 94).

With José Dubach's arrival, these bad experiences were corrected. Dubach implemented a technology transfer process in Salinas, with which the inhabitants began to produce different types of cheese: fresh, semi-ripe, and mature (Naranjo et al., 2018). This process was practical, in accordance with the logic of trial and error, with which it is possible to apply and perfect the acquired knowledge (Delgado, 2022).

This process of technology transfer allowed the development of other community productive activities, each of these carried out with love and commitment in any development process (Polo, 2021).

We had very specific and free advice, it is important to emphasize, people who knew Salinas, the processes of change in the parish, retirees who knew about the subject of chocolate making who came here and contributed their knowledge to the making of chocolates. For example, there is a living professor who is with the Salesians with whom the first chocolate refining machines were designed, these machines were built with personnel from here, with the salineros, some who were studying mechanical engineering and were able to contribute... the first chocolates that were made were thanks to an Italian couple who came to Salinas, we went from making cocoa derivatives, such as paste for companies, to final consumers with the chocolates (Interviewee 3).

This interview highlights the importance of knowledge transfer, in which local knowledge is combined with that of the expert. Community participation is relevant from the definition of the problem to its solution. In this case, the type of social technology focuses on processes and products, which allows for the improvement of the population's living conditions through deliberate actions between various actors that make better use of existing endogenous resources (Mballa, 2017).

Third stage: Decentralisation of the productive system

In this period, the objective is to diversify production systems, so that residents become involved in activities to develop new products (Naranjo et al., 2018).

Well, as a result of the cheese factory venture, it was also seen that it was necessary to implement some sources of work. So, with the whey that came from the dairy production from the cheese factories, we said, what will we do with this product? So, through the cooperative, they decided to give credits for raising pigs and thus take advantage of the whey from the cheese factories...the idea of making sausages came up, mainly because...we have to add this product to the commercialisation of dairy products...so that is how the sausage factory was born” (Interviewee 4).

From this interview, it is worth highlighting the ability to add value to raw materials, which, according to Amaril Filho (1999) cited in Tenório & Monje-Reyes, (2010) a characteristic of local development at the economic level. The main task is for each community to seek a specific identity:

Some have already come close: Apahua with trout farming and fishing, Yarauksha with the llama meat sausage factory, Natawa with nougat factories and with the specialisation in sheep farming, Yacubiana with the extraordinary diversification of dairy products, Matiaví with panela and its derivatives, Chaupi with cabuya, Mulidihuan with bamboo, La Palma with jams and Chazohuan, the community that has had the most opportunities to diversify its economy with its sugar mill, chocolate, fish farming, sausage factory, mill and feed mill. (Polo, 2021, p. 135)

The above demonstrates the importance of citizen participation and inclusion in production processes. In this participatory exercise, the following stages were completed (Naranjo et al., 2018):

- Development of a grassroots organisation focused on community savings and credit.
- Training and infrastructure are necessary for the development of production processes.
- Technical assistance and support with training and productive projects in the communities that make up Salinas, by FUNORSAL.

The successes in productive initiatives allowed the promotion of socioeconomic processes with the participation of the organization's members and, in most cases, with the help of volunteers, thus achieving social profitability over financial profitability (Naranjo et al., 2018).

A third pillar is the question of the interns and volunteers who have come here, some Italian and Chilean volunteers have come here... they have spent one or two years and have been leaving their knowledge... Salinas... managed to... get out of a situation of poverty, a situation that improved your quality of life (Interviewee 1)

FUNORSAL, who in some way began to support the transfer of all the technology from Salinas and in this way each of the 30 communities in 24 have cheese plants (Interviewee 6).

From these interviews, it is important to highlight the re-application of Social Technologies in the communities of Salinas to promote transformation processes and thus achieve better living conditions for people. Likewise, it is important to mention how the communities have benefited from using financial surpluses to construct works within their communities (Naranjo et al., 2018). When considering the stages of the community process in Salinas de Guaranda, it can be seen that a particular contribution of social technology marked each one. In the first stage, characterized by community participation, the creation of decision-making spaces and the recognition of the importance of citizens in collective decision-making through dialogue stand out, which fostered understanding among its members. In the second stage of the community process, the contribution of social technology was characterized by the importance of knowledge transfer.

The participation of the expert, who provided quality information transparently and understandably, was fundamental in each of the local processes carried out in Salinas. Finally, the third stage was characterized by the re-application of technology. In this stage, it is essential to understand the local context, take advantage of endogenous resources, and establish participation relationships with other regional actors, which generates spaces for understanding and transparency. The Table 2 presents the contributions of social technologies in each stage through which the community process has passed. It identifies each of the categories previously identified in Table 1.

Table 2. Contributions of social technology to local development in Salinas de Guaranda

Stage	Type of Social Technology Used	Contribution of social technology to local development in Salinas	Social Technology Category
1. Construction of physical infrastructure	About Organization	Participation of the local community throughout the process, from defining the problem to implementing the solution.	Discussion process
			Inclusion
			Pluralism
			Participatory equality
			Autonomy
2. Develop production and marketing systems	From Process	Local knowledge is combined with expert or technical knowledge (often foreign), which is not neglected but integrated and assimilated. It seeks to benefit from local skills and experiences, as well as from local resources, endogenous resources.	Common good
			Inclusion
			Pluralism
			Participatory equality
			Autonomy
3. Decentralisation of the productive system.	About Product	Look for possibilities for re-application. Re-applicability means that when a social technology is to be implemented in a different	Discussion process
			Inclusion
			Pluralism
			Participatory equality
			Autonomy

		<p>context than the one in which it was developed, it will necessarily be adapted or rethought according to local needs, with the possibility of adding new values and meanings.</p>	<p>Common good:</p>
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Own elaboration

Limitations of The Study

This study focused on a specific community, Salinas de Guaranda in Ecuador, and on a qualitative methodological approach. While this allowed for a deep understanding of the local context and experience, the nature of the case study limits the generalizability of the findings to other communities. The socioeconomic, cultural and geographic conditions of Salinas de Guaranda are unique. What worked in this community may not be replicable in others with different characteristics; however, the study can provide general principles on the successful implementation of social technology, such as the importance of community participation, adaptation to local needs and the combination of external knowledge with local knowledge. The case of Salinas de Guaranda can serve as a source of inspiration and learning for other rural communities seeking development alternatives.

Conclusions and Recommendations

In the first stage of the community process, Social Technologies of the Organisation type were fundamental for satisfying basic needs: water, light, and viability. Thus, they improved the living conditions of the population and created spaces of solidarity and cooperative actions. These conditions are for Tenório and Monje-Reyes (2010) characteristics of local development.

The second stage, characterized by social process technology, was distinguished by the transfer of knowledge, mainly from the expert (often foreign), who integrates, assimilates and benefits from local skills and experiences (Vaujany et al., 2015). Salinas de Guaranda has received constant support, especially from foreigners who have selflessly transmitted knowledge to improve living conditions.

In the third stage, social technology as a product becomes more relevant, characterized by re-application; that is, when a social technology is going to be used in a different context than the one in which it was developed, it will be adapted to the needs of the locality, adding new values and meanings (Vaujany et al., 2015). The participation of various actors in the diversification and commercialisation of products is crucial for greater value addition (Tenório & Monjes-Reyes, 2010).

The social technologies (organisation, processes, and products) in Salinas de Guaranda, which are free to access and without copyright restrictions, benefit the community through training and knowledge transfer. These technologies respond to social needs, with people as the main drivers

of their development. They have improved the quality of life, reduced poverty and exclusion, and significantly transformed their reality.

Since this study focused on a specific case, comparative research with other rural communities, both inside and outside Ecuador, is suggested to explore the diversity of experiences with social technology. It is also recommended that the long-term impact of these technologies on community development be further analysed, considering socioeconomic, environmental, and gender variables. It is also relevant to investigate the role of public policies and the participation of different actors in the implementation and sustainability of social technology initiatives.

References

- Álvarez - Gayou, J. (2003). *How to do qualitative research: fundamentals and methodology*. Paidós Educador.
- Bernal, C. (2010). *Research methodology.-administration, economics, humanities and social sciences (3rd edition)*. Pearson Education.
- Binimelis -Espinoza, H. (2017). Electronic government as a technology for social inclusion. *Reflections from SocialWork*. Catholic University of Temuco (UCT). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/1982-02592017v20n3p448>
- Calanchez, A., Rios, M., Zevallos, R., & Silva, F. (2022). Innovation and social entrepreneurship as a strategy to face the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Journal of Social Sciences (Ve)*, XXVII (1), 275-287. <https://doi.org/10.31876/rcs.v28i1.37691>
- Cardoso, A., Tenório, F. & Pereira, J. (2019). *Social Management: Epistemology of a Paradigm*.
- Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean. (2021). *Social Panorama of Latin America 2020*.
- Delgado, A. (2022). Technological contribution to the development of the main cheese factory in Salinas, in the province of Bolívar. *Estudios de la Gestión*, N° 11, 121-149. <https://doi.org/10.32719/25506641.2022.11.4>
- Gómez, R. (2021). *Technology and society. A political philosophy*. Buenos Aires, Ciccus Foundation.
- Martínez, P. (2006). The case study method: methodological strategy of scientific research. *Pensamiento & Gestión*, (20), 165-193. <https://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=64602005>
- Mballa, L. (2017). Local development and microfinance as strategies to address social needs: a theoretical-conceptual approach. *Mexican Journal of Political and Social Sciences*, 229. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0185-1918\(17\)30005-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0185-1918(17)30005-3)

Naranjo, K. (2012). *Local Culture and Management*. (PhD Thesis). Doctoral Program in Administration, Andean University Simon Bolivar, Ecuador Campus.

Naranjo, K., Abad, A., & Ramos, V. (2018). Cultural factors of achievement of the community production system of the parish Salinas in the province of Bolívar, Ecuador. *Chakiñan Magazine*, 2018, N°6, 136-148. <https://doi.org/10.37135/chk.002.06.09>

Polo, A. (2021). The lagoon of dreams.-Between the memories of the past and the visions of the future of a Salesian missionary in the Ecuadorian Andes. Quito, ABYA YALA

Samaniego, K. (2021). *Analysis of the popular and solidarity economy sector as a key mechanism for poverty reduction. Case study: Parish of Salinas de Guaranda 1974 – 2020*. (Undergraduate thesis). Faculty of Economics. Pontifical Catholic University of Ecuador.

Sosa, M., Riquelme, Y. & Diez, O (2020). Considerations on local development. *University and Society Journal*, 12(4), 309-315.

Tenório, F. & Monje-Reyes, P. (2010). *Citizenship, participation and local development*. Editorial-ARCIS

Torres, M. & Naranjo, K. (2022). Social Technology in Ecuador. *Venezuelan Journal of Management*, 27(99), 1215-1230. <https://doi.org/10.52080/rvgluz.27.99.23>

Treacy, M. (2022). Dependency Theory and the Critique of Neodevelopmentalism in Latin America. *Latin American Perspectives*, Issue 242, Vol. 49 No. 1. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0094582X211066531>

Vaujany, F., Mitev, N., Lanzara, G. & Mukherjee, A. (2015). Technology. Work and Globalization. *Palgrave MacMillan*. ISBN: 978-0-230-01873-0.